

A 298

16 NOV 93

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 16 / 11 / 193 TAKE OFF 1000 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A298
LANDING 1701.

PROJECT OFFICER :

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE
FLIGHT LEADER: M. SMITH
OBSERVER: MARSS S ENGLISH
OTHERS: CCN ~~FERRIS~~ D. LAUHLAN
FILTERS D. PERLIVAL
VACC C. O'DOWD
CLOUD PH. A. McHAFFIE

CAPTAIN: H. HENDERSON
CO-PILOT: H. BURLOYNE
NAVIGATOR: J. CANNING
ENGINEER: K. QUICK
LOADMASTER: R. PRICE

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s) :

OPERATING AREA:

NORTH WEST OF IRELAND

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME: 12Z

A298 16th November, 1993

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
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100446		Take off from FARNBOROUGH		
101413(1)-102819(2)		Run 1 (in Transit)	FL90	315 deg
103018(3)-103857(4)		Run 2 (in Transit)	FL90	340 deg
115247(5)-122739(11)		Profile P1	FL260->60ft	290/005
122854(12)-123058(13)		K-gamma Run 3.1	100ft	185 deg
123400(14)-123521(15)		K-gamma Run 3.2	100ft	005 deg
123623(16)-123737(17)		ORBIT 1 LWD, 45deg	250ft	start 270 deg
123900(18)-124403(19)		Run 4.1	100ft	265 deg
124531(20)-125034(21)		Run 4.2	100ft	075 deg
125209(22)-125711(24)		Run 4.3	100ft	265 deg
125855(25)-130355(26)		Run 4.4	100ft	075 deg
130355(26)-133535(37)		Profile P2	100ft->2000ft	
130929(28)-131429(29)		Run 5.1	1000ft	260 deg
131547(30)-132049(31)		Run 5.2	1000ft	080 deg
132206(32)-132709(33)		Run 5.3	1000ft	260 deg
132826(34)-133327(35)		Run 5.4	1000ft	080 deg
133806(38)-134311(39)		Run 6.1	2000ft	265 deg
134446(40)-134942(41)		Run 6.2	2000ft	080 deg
135057(42)-135557(43)		Run 6.3	2000ft	265 deg
135712(45)-140212(45)		Run 6.4	2000ft	085 deg

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
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140407(46)	-140931(47)	Run 7.1	FL60	240 deg
141026(48)	-141524(49)	Run 7.2	FL60	100 deg
141631(50)	-142132(51)	Run 7.3	FL60	260 deg
142242(52)	-142740(53)	Run 7.4	FL60	090 deg
143014(54)	-143349(55)	Run 8.1	8250ft	360 deg
143507(56)	-144008(57)	Run 8.2	8250ft	090 deg
144123(58)	-144536(59)	Run 8.3	8250ft	240 deg
144633(61)	-145121(62)	Run 8.4	8250ft	005 deg
145729(64)	-151818(65)	Profile P3	100ft->FL150	150 deg
170103		Land at FARNBOROUGH		

Aircraft Scientist Debrief: A298

Variation of Aerosol/CCN Composition and Concentration VACC

Flight A298 was carried out on 16 November 1993. A very successful sortie was flown to the North West of Ireland. As for flight A297 we flew to the west of a frontal area to sample in the clear air high wind region behind the front.

The problems with the Laser on A297 were determined to be due to the differential pressure between the cabin and the exterior of the aircraft. By operating unpressurised below 9,000 ft and with minimal increase in cabin pressure above that height we were able to operate successfully.

SORTIE BRIEF: 16 NOVEMBER 1993

Variation of Aerosol Composition and Concentration VACC

1) **SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To determine the vertical structure of sea-salt and non-sea-salt sulphate aerosol in a clean marine boundary layer.

2) **LOCATION:** Northeast Atlantic, ^{57½N 12W}~~53-54N 11-17W~~. The sortie will be conducted directly up-wind of (and in the same air mass as) the Mace Head ground based research station.

3) **WEATHER:** Non-precipitating, moderate to high wind region in the cyclone system tracking across the N. Atlantic. Air trajectory must be purely maritime.

4) FLIGHT PATTERN:

- a. Conduct a 20 minute VACC run at about 10,000 ft to validate correct operation as soon after take off ^{TRANSITION AT FL100} as suitable. If no problems are apparent then continue.
- b. Transit over Ireland to sampling location and approx 20K ft (2hr 10min) ^{TRANSIT RUN 2}
- c. Execute a profile to 50ft in cloud free air, if possible, @ 1000ft/min then, once in the marine boundary layer, profile @ 500ft/min (30min) ^(step-down)
- d. Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min)
^{45°, left wing down ORBIT for MACE. 100ft.}
- e. VACC horizontal runs will be conducted at (1) 100ft above sea-level (25min), (2) just below cloud base (25min), (3) 500ft above cloud base (25min) and (4) above cloud top (25min). Each VACC run will comprise two figure-of-eight race tracks across wind direction (total of four 5-minute legs, one for each heater tube, and a one minute turn). If a decoupled marine boundary layer exists, then an extra VACC run (25min) will be required just above the surface-subcloud layer inversion. VACC runs in cloud will depend on cloud size. In between VACC run profile at 500ft/min
- f. On completion of stack, terminate the scientific part of the flight with a profile down to 50ft @ 500ft/min (30min).
- g. Transit back to base (1hr 50min)

TOTAL DURATION Transit 4 hrs
 VACC 3-3.5hrs

Request diplomatic clearance to transit over Ireland

A298 16-NOV-93

GPS data
09:19:25 - 17:07:05

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 16/11/93

Flight No: A 298 Page 1 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1609.57	00	TR	5.9	F	324	51.63	-1.5	Ground Fog Solid cloud overhead.	
10.14.13	01	R1	90	FL	305	51.85	-1.84	Ground fog Patchy in valleys. 8/8 Sc overhead.	
10.17.00	01	R1	89	FL	312	52.05	-2.16	Low Sc just above ground 8/8 Sc Above.	
10.24.34	01	R1	89	FL	318	/	/	Mazy no ground fog dramatic change in p.casp 8/8 Sc above	
10.28.20	01	R1	89	FL	301	/	/	Mazy & clear snow on hill tops in distance	
10.30.16	01	R2	9.0	FL	305	/	/	Mazy & clear some bands of cu ahead 8/8 Sc overhead.	
10.34.57	01	R2	8.8	FL	329	/	/	Clear Below low st cu ahead 8/8 Sc above	
10.44.49	04	Climb	15.2	FL	331	/	/	Mazy below 4/8 st cu more solid ahead. heavy 8/8 Sc above.	
10.55.46	04	Climb	24.2	FL	328	54.19	-4.52	request reduced cabin pressure to test voice	
11.01.00	04	Climb	25.8	FL	326	54.51	-4.79	in ci	
11.02.34	04	Climb	25.8	FL	326	54.6	-4.87	Cabin testing nsasp-x cabin den 15 kft. lower below 40	
11.09.03	04	Thrus	25.8	FL	318	55.07	-5.41	6/4 st cu below thin ci above cabin requested unpressurized below 8/8	

15 → 30

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VITEC Date: 16/11/93

Flight No: 4298 Page 3 of 7

used
8000
ft.

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12.22.02		P1	2.3	P	174	57.16	-12.09	cut top 2000 ft. main tops 7000 ca base 1500 ft.	
12.25.12		P1	6.7	P	185	57.04	-12.08	Hazy 4/8 cu above 35-40 kts southerly.	
12.27.44		P1	600 ft	R	217	57.00	-12.13	Hazy. Sea state 6 1017	
12.28.54		R ^{3.1} R ^{1.8}	1000 ft	R	175	56.71	-12.20	KX cum 15-20 ft swell.	
12.31.00		R ^{3.1} R ^{1.8}	1000 ft	R					
12.34.00		R ^{3.2} KX	100	R	357	56.87	-12.20	4/8 cu above 100-135.	
12.35.21		R ^{3.2} KX	100	R					
12.36.23		01	250	R					
12.37.37		encl 01	250	R					
12.39.00		4.1	100	R	264			hazy bumpy 4/8 cu above.	
12.44.04		encl 4.1	100	R	251	56.75	-12.85	hazy ci sun shining through 4/8 cu. DOP	NO NAS AIDS!
12.45.32		4.2	100	R	62	56.44	-12.79		

1000
2500 | 1500
7500
F

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 16/11/93

Flight No: A298 Page 2 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:13:35	04	TR	25.8	FL	296	55.31	-5.81	7/8 Sc ^{low} below thin veil of Ci above.	
11:30:30	04	TR	25.9	FL	294	55.97	-7.82	very thin ci above. 8/8 hazy sc below.	
11:36:06	04	TR	25.9	FL	285	56.15	-8.47	just skimming the top of Ci clear above.	
11:44:03	04	TR	25.9	FL	285	56.55	-9.40	in thin ci 2/8 streets of cu visible at low level.	
11:52:46	05	P1	26.0	FL	268	56.49	-10.17	3/8 sc below 1/8 sc middle level within level of ci	
12:01:53	05	P1	16.3	FL	262	56.52	-11.52	2/8 cu below 8/8 ci above thin hazy ci.	
12:05:14	07	inter P1	12.8	FL	292	56.52	-11.86	8/8 ci above 7/8 sc below.	
12:06:10	08	vo com P1	12.7	FL	350	56.58	-11.89	7/8 cu below ending in line on horiz ahead	
12:12:14	08	P1	790	FL	349	-57	-11.94	Reduce decent Rate to 500ft/min. 7000 crp	
								aerosol level @ 7 1/2 K.	7000
12:17:04	08	P1	420	FL	348	-57.29	-12.00	below sc layer. 4/8 cu bands below.	
12:18:54	10	P1	390	FL	185	57.30	-12.08		

720 55
45

10
14
4
3
17

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 16/11/98

Flight No: A298 Page 4 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12.50.35	21	^{end} R4.2	100	K	67	57.10	-12.40	hazy 4/8 cu ci above.	185 25-70kt
12.52.11	22	R4.3	100	R	255	57.07	-12.44		
12.57.10	24	^{end} R4.3	100	R	253	57.05	-12.86		
12.58.54	25	R4.4	100	R	62	57.02	-12.08	4/8 cu hazy ci & Blue sky above	
13:03:54	26	R4.1 /R2	100	K	63	57.15	-12.49	hazy 4/8 cu above.	
1305.13	27	R2.1	1000	R	172	57.10	-12.35		
13:08:27	28	R5.1	1000	R	251	57.01	12.43	hazy 4/8 cu above some ci above that.	
13:14:29	29	^e R5.1	1000	R	203	56.96	-12.84	hazy 4/8 cu above	5m N & W 4m E.
13.15.47	30	R5.2	1000	R	66	56.85	-12.77	very hazy 4/8 cu above	
13.20.51	31	^e R5.2	1000	R	66	57.10	-12.34	very hazy about 200 ft below cloud base	
13 22.07	32	R5.3	1000	R	250	57.08	-12.39		
13.27.09	33	^{end} R5.3	1000	R	249	57.04	-12.80		

30

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13.28.86	34	5.4	4000 rad		65	57.03	-12.71		
13.33.27	35	end 5.4	1000			57.18	-12.30	Mazy ci directly ahead. Cats of an ahead.	
13.35.35	37	inter P2	2000		170	57.10	-12.25	cloud base @ 1500 climb to 2000 ft.	
13.38.06	38	6.1	2000		249	57.02	-12.29	13.36.54 into cloud	
13.43.11	39	end 6.1	2000		245	56.99	-12.69	Sc above in small cum layer.	
13.44.46	40	6.2	2000 R		67	56.99	-12.57		
13.49.42	41	end 6.2	2000 R		68	57.14	-12.18	in cu.	
13.50.57	42	6.3	2000 R		250	57.11	-12.21		
13.55.59	43	end 6.3	2000 R		250	57.07	-12.62		
13.57.15	44	6.4	2000 R		68	8		in and out of cu. in cloud notes on PA send.	
14.02.12	45	end 6.4	2000 R			57.20	-12.11	5000 cloud top	
14.04.07	46	7.1	600	F1	227	57.17	-12.19	4/8 cu some s/c below 7/8 ci above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 16/11/93

Flight No: A298 Page 6 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14.09.32	47	end 7.1	FL60			57.02 -12.56	4/8 SC + 4/8 CU below.		
14.10.26	48	7.2	60	FL	87	57.00 -12.50	3/8 CU below. 4/8 SC above.		
14.15.24	49	end 7.2	60	FL		57.06 -12.01	Change of air mass at this level. NOTE. cloud above. 4/8 CU below.		
14.20.00	247	end 7.3	5.9K P		248	57.00 -12.32	Pass over boundary small CU into SC.		
14.21.31	247	end 7.3	5.9K P		240	56.98 -12.45			
14.22.45	248	7.4	5.9K P		76	56.96 -12.37			
14.27.40		end 7.4	5.9K				end of run over 2/8 CU.		
14.30.14	54	8.1	8250 P		228	57.00 -12.04	into aerosol layer CI above 6/8 CU below.		
14.33.48	55	end 8.1	8250 P		228	56.90 -12.28			
14.35.07	56	8.2	8250 P		79	56.88 -12.20	4/8 CU below CI above SC above at head.		
14.40.09	57	8.2	8250 P		80	56.79 -11.69	6/8 CU below CI above.		
14.41.23	58	start 8.3	8250 P		229	56.95 -11.70	5/8 CU below 2/8 SC above 8/8 CI above that		

8000
4x2x2

~~56.40~~
56.40
1200
surface
propagating
out

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 16/11/93

Flight No: A298 Page 7 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14.43.38	59	^{end} 8.3	8250	P	270	56.80	-11.81	6/8 cu below 8/8 sc above.	
14.46.33	61	8.4	8250	P	350	52.86	-11.84	4/8 cu below 8/8 sc above.	
14.51.21	62	^{end} 8.4	8250	P	352	57.20	-11.91	4/8 cu below 8/8 sc above sky in horizon	
14.57.38	63	P3	100	R	136	57.31	-11.72	Very hazy. Some cu visible above. Sea state 7-8	
15.05.12	64	P3	4:6K	P	140	57.17	-11.42	cloud tops just above 4 1/2K	
15.13.51	64	P3	10.2K	P	131	56.85	-10.78	7/8 sc below 8/8 ci above.	
15.17.54	6								
15.18.18	65	^{end} P3	150	P	138	56.79	-10.40	8/8 sc below entering cirrus layer.	

BOOM OPERATORS LOG

D PERCIVAL

FLIGHT A29P

DATE 16 11 193

PROJECT VACC

PART 1 of 2

G.M.T.	HEIGHT	I.A.S.	RUN	FILTER	POS.N	PUMP	REMARKS	
111115	FL 260	200	TRANSIT	#124	IB	386004	Pump On	
			CABIN TEST	CONTROL.	1631		Boom Out	
			Includes answer "smoke" brackets 1115-1130					Boom In
115235	FL 260 ^{1600' DRON}	190	Run			387635	Pump Off	
123911	100 ft	180	Run 4.1	#133	IB	387635	Pump On	
123948			↓		938	387662	Boom Out	
130420					1041	388600	Boom In	
130436			Run 4.4			388676	Pump off.	
131028	1000ft	180	Run 5.1	#126	IB	388676	Pump On	
131107			↓		961	388739	Boom Out	
133330						389600	Boom In	
133429			Run 5.4			389630	Pump off	
134050	2000ft	180	Run 6.1	#103	IB	389630	Pump On	
134147			↓		1279	389663	Boom Out	
140228			↓			390942	Boom In	
140328			Run 6.4			390991	Pump off.	

A228 16 NOV 92 12:22:12 091 0.20 0.90 F.P.

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
313.	728.	8.9	301.	-4.2	-36.4	223/7

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

↓ 2.2 !

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC	#/cc	149
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.08
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	0.45
FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.0
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00
2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 10:24:53

A258

16 NOV 93

10:50:30

094

54.22

4.55

FL P

HDG deg T 327.	SPR mb 382.	PHGT kft 24.7	TAS knots 231.	TAT C -39.1	DEW C -37.1	WIND deg m/s 233/15
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A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A278

16 NOV 92

19:59:12

004

54.38

4.58

F.F.P.

HDG deg T 327.	SPR mb 363.	PHGT kft 25.8	TAS knots 237.	TAT C -41.7	DEW C -40.3	WIND deg m/s 234/18
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AGE OF

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T 291.	SPR mb 362.	PHGT kft 25.9	TAS knots 305.	TAT C -42.5	DEW C -48.9	WIND deg m/s 247/11	
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PLOT 1 102604

PLOT 2 103858

PLOT 3 110639

A SELECT	B CCNMEN	C HOLD	D SINGLE	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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H298 16-NOV-93 11:51:43 004 32 50.50 -10.25 PK F

HDG degT 267.	SPR mb 360.	PHGT kft 26.0	TAS knots 275.	TAT C -41.9	DEW C -41.2	WIND deg m/s 222/20	
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A SELECT	B	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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* START PROFILE P1 *

A298 16-NOV-93 12:05:30 007 -- 56.52 -11.85 AS P

286. 621. 12.9 211. -13.4 -13.2 218/21

A	F	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAM	FREQ	COOR			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 68
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.09
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 10.94

FSSP CONC #/cc 1
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.5
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 2.4
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:06:47

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 78
 PCASP MEAN RAD μ 0.08
 PCASP MASS $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 0.28

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD μ 0.6
 FSSP LWC g/m^3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE μ 0
 2D-C LWC g/m^3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:13:50

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1 0.1 10
 1 0.1 10

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC #/cc 81
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.14
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 6.69

FSSP CONC #/cc 6
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.9
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:24:11

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1 0.1
1 0.1

H298

16-NOV-53

12:31:42

010

50.81

12.20

5R

HDG deg T 245.	SPR mb 999.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 188.	TAT C 9.2	DEW C 6.9	WIND deg m/s 181/15
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GE OF

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC	#/cc	135
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.13
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	11.76

FSSP CONC	#/cc	6
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.8
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:33:21

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1 0.1
1 0.1

10
10

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC #/cc 88
 PCASP MEAN RAD μ 0.18
 PCASP MASS $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 29.00

FSSP CONC #/cc 5
 FSSP MEAN RAD μ 0.9
 FSSP LWC g/m^3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE μ 0
 2D-C LWC g/m^3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:44:37

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC	#/cc	112
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.16
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	18.42

FSSP CONC	#/cc	6
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.7
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.5
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 12:56:38

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

1000 1000

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC	#/cc	59
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.15
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	13.23
FSSP CONC	#/cc	3
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	1.5
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00
2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 13:41:20

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

10
10

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC	#/cc	57
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.14
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	12.23

FSSP CONC	#/cc	2
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	1.5
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 13:49:36

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1	0.1	10
1	0.1	10

A298 16-NOV-93 14:03:09 045 57.19 -12.12 AS P

231. 877. 3.9 174. 1.1 -1.0 188/19

R-G- 1212.91

H	B	L	D	E	F	S	H
SELECT	PARAS	FPED	ZOOM			WIDE:	HELP

A298

16-NOV-93

14:15:42

049

57.05 -12.00

AS P

HDC deg T	SPR ms	PHGT kts	TAE knots	TOT C	DEW C	WIND deg / s
125.	814.	5.9	204.	-0.8	-21.9	191/21

NOTE
K

291.35

deg F
kts

5.94

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC #/cc 190
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.09
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 1.13

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 14:27:11

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
 1000

1

0.1
 0.1

10
 10

PCASP CONC/cc

2000

PCASP CONC #/cc 227
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.08
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.63

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 14:33:42

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1 0.1 10
 1 0.1 10

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC	#/cc	323
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.00
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	1.00

FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.0
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 14:42:28

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 58
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.09
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.31

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-16 14:52:25

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1	0.1	10
1	0.1	10

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

0

PCASP CONC	#/cc	33
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.07
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	0.05

FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.0
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-16 15:15:25

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A298 16-NOV-93 15:19:06 065 56.77 -10.36 AS P

139. 549. 16.0 224. -19.5 -20.6 225/25

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAMS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A298

16 NOV 95

15:23:21

365

56.65

-2.92

FL 0

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
121.	433.	21.7	224.	-31.9	-31.4	214/25

POTE
K

308.82

PHGTF
Kft

21.73

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A298 16 NOV 93 15:52:24 295 55.44 6.30 FRP

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
159.	379.	24.8	315.	-38.6	-43.3	251/10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDEO	HELP

A298 16-NOV-93 15:27:36 065 -- 56.51 -9.36 AS P

ALT	BARO	TEMP	TAS	CRS	DEW	WIND
feet	hPa	deg C	knots	deg	deg C	deg/s
127.	379.	24.8	267.	-39.4	-38.1	221/22

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

ASXV EGRRT 27 16-NOV-93.

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:10m

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

GACA
57.1N 20.3W
AT 11Z
10 -60
15 -58
20 -60
T 214 -68

100	180	59
85	185	59
80	185	59
70	190	59
60	190	59
50	195	56
40	190	55
30	200	52
25	200	48
20	210	50
15	215	38
10	235	41
MAX	27902	
	255	73

STORNOWAY
03026
AT 11Z
10 -60
15 -61
20 -65
T 217 -66

100	205	22
	205	27
85	215	25
80	220	24
70	230	27
60	235	25
50	245	29
40	245	25
30	240	35
25	245	40
20	240	41
15	260	27
10	220	29
MAX	29571	
T	270	92

TRAPPES
07145
AT 11Z
10 -61
15 -63
20 -66
T 183 -70

100	115	8
	075	23
85	070	24
80	065	24
70	055	26
60	030	24
50	340	15
40	285	8
30	285	17
25	285	23
20	285	30
15	290	28
10	290	30
MAX	8<ME	
	290	80

DE BILT
06260
10 -61
15 -62
20 -67
T 209 -67

100	095	9
	065	12
85	065	18
80	050	20
70	030	21
60	010	18
50	345	16
40	315	13
30	330	24
25	320	31
20	310	37
15	310	17
10	295	31

SCHLESWIG
10035
AT 11Z
10 -61
15 -63
20 -68
T 204 -69

100	045	6
	045	8
85	040	18
80	035	22
70	020	24
60	010	23
50	010	22
40	355	33
30	340	34
25	325	35
20	320	35
15	335	24
10	310	24

BORDEAUX
07510
10 -62
15 -63
20 -66
T 204 -67

100	075	11
	090	26
85	090	30
80	090	27
70	070	21
60	010	13
50	315	10
40	295	23
30	295	20
25	285	27
20	280	39
15	295	35
10	295	28

DE BILT
06260

10-61
15-62
20-67
T 209-67

100	095	9
	065	12
85	065	18
80	050	20
70	030	21
60	010	18
50	345	16
40	315	13
30	330	24
25	320	31
20	310	37
15	310	17
10	295	36
MAX	NIL	

SCHLESWIG
10035
AT 11Z

10-61
15-63
20-68
T 204-69

100	045	6
	045	8
85	040	18
80	035	22
70	020	24
60	010	23
50	010	22
40	355	33
30	340	34
25	325	35
20	320	35
15	355	24
10	310	26
MAX	NIL	

BORDEAUX
07510

10-62
15-63
20-66
T 204-67

100	075	11
	090	26
85	090	30
80	090	27
70	070	21
60	010	13
50	315	10
40	295	23
30	295	20
25	285	27
20	280	39
15	295	35
10	285	28
MAX	7(MB)	
	290	89

THORSHAYN
06011
AT 11Z

10-64
15-58
20-61
T 232-67

100	240	22
	250	27
85	250	28
80	255	32
70	260	50
60	250	44
50	265	43
40	275	46
30	280	46
25	270	53
20	245	50
15	240	57

LARKHILL
03743
AT 11Z

10-62
15-62
20-64
T 226-63

100	140	14
	135	17
85	125	17
80	115	11
70	205	12
60	245	15
50	245	22
40	245	31
30	220	24
25	230	34
20	215	19
15	260	24

STAVANGER
01415

10-62
15-61
20-65
T 215-66

100	175	41
	195	37
85	215	38
80	225	33
70	230	26
60	235	23
50	270	31
40	260	36
30	285	30
25	280	34
20	285	35
15	260	21

THORSHAVN
 06011
 AT 11Z
 10 -64
 15 -58
 20 -61
 T 252 -67

100	240	22
	250	27
85	250	28
80	255	32
70	260	50
60	250	44
50	265	43
40	275	46
30	280	43
25	270	53
20	245	50
15	240	37
10	245	32
MAX	NIL	

LARKHILL
 03743
 AT 11Z
 10 -62
 15 -62
 20 -64
 T 226 -63

100	140	14
	135	17
85	125	17
80	115	11
70	205	12
60	245	15
50	245	22
40	245	31
30	220	24
25	230	34
20	215	19
15	260	24
10	290	23
MAX	NIL	

STAVANGER
 01415
 10 -62
 15 -61
 20 -65
 T 215 -66

100	175	41
	195	37
85	215	38
80	225	33
70	230	26
60	235	23
50	270	31
40	260	36
30	285	30
25	280	34
20	285	35
15	260	21
10	275	25
MAX	28151	
T	270	59

LERWICK
03005
AT 11Z
10-61
15-62
20-63
T 237-65

100	230	22
	235	27
85	230	25
90	230	24
70	245	27
60	250	31
50	260	33
40	250	47
30	250	55
25	250	57
20	240	38
15	265	37
10	250	27
MAX	NIL	

UCCLE
06447
AT 11Z
10-60
15-63
20-66
T 183-67

100	075	12
	070	20
85	065	26
80	055	27
70	045	27
60	020	26
50	005	18
40	340	15
30	330	26
25	325	27
20	315	29
15	310	23
10	295	31
MAX	26322	
	275	58

BOULMER
03240
AT 11Z
10-62
15-62
20-63
T 216-66

100	220	13
	240	25
85	225	33
80	230	32
70	235	35
60	245	27
50	245	23
40	245	32
30	240	37
25	255	44
20	255	32
15	265	23
10	260	26
MAX	NIL	

LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z
10-62
15-64
20-64
T 210-65

100	205	29
	210	31
85	210	36
80	200	28
70	220	43
60	225	26
50	225	22
40	225	30
30	225	33
25	250	28
20	235	29
15	260	37
10	255	25
MAX	NIL	

RAUGHTON
03322
AT 11Z
10-61
15-61
20-65
T 213-66

100	190	18
	200	21
85	205	17
80	210	18
70	230	25
60	235	31
50	245	34
40	225	20
30	235	32
25	230	48
20	240	33
15	260	26
10	255	23
MAX	24506	
	270	55

HENSBY
03496
AT 11Z
10-62
15-62
20-67
T 193-68

100	180	4
	175	12
85	140	5
80	095	7
70	280	7
60	275	12
50	295	33
40	255	24
30	265	23
25	270	29
20	280	31
15	285	21
10	265	20
MAX	NIL	

LONG KESH

LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z
10 -62
15 -64
20 -64
T 210 -65

100	205	29
	210	31
85	210	36
80	200	28
70	220	43
60	225	26
50	225	22
40	225	30
30	225	33
25	250	28
20	235	29
15	260	37
10	255	25
MAX	NIL	

RUGHTON
03322
AT 11Z
10 -61
15 -61
20 -65
T 213 -66

100	190	18
	200	21
85	205	17
80	210	18
70	230	25
60	235	31
50	245	34
40	225	20
30	235	32
25	230	48
20	240	33
15	260	26
10	255	23
MAX	24506	
	270	65

HEMSBY
03496
AT 11Z
10 -62
15 -62
20 -67
T 193 -68

100	180	4
	175	12
85	140	5
80	095	7
70	280	7
60	275	12
50	295	33
40	255	24
30	265	23
25	270	29
20	280	31
15	285	21
10	265	20
MAX	NIL	

VALENTIA
03953
10 -61
15 -61
20 -63
T 227 -62

100	165	36
	170	32
85	175	29
80	190	34
70	195	35
60	200	24
50	230	17
40	225	17
30	230	30
25	245	24
20	245	24
15	245	24
10	245	24
MAX	NIL	

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 11Z
10 -61
15 -61
20 -60
T 237 -61

100	150	30
	145	26
85	155	8
80	195	25
70	195	25
60	190	30
50	195	42
40	215	21
30	195	26
25	215	19
20	215	19
15	215	19
10	215	19
MAX	NIL	

HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 11Z
10 -64
15 -63
20 -67
T 188 -68

100	100	10
	120	13
85	120	19
80	110	12
70	130	6
60	305	8
50	290	19
40	250	15
30	235	16
25	250	18
20	250	18
15	250	18
10	250	18
MAX	NIL	

VALENTIA
03953
10 -61
15 -61
20 -63
T 227 -62

100	165	36
85	170	32
80	175	29
70	190	34
60	195	35
50	200	24
40	225	17
30	230	30
25	245	34
20	245	32
15		
10	235	27
MAX	28151	
	270	84

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 117
10 -61
15 -61
20 -60
T 237 -61

100	150	30
35	145	26
80	155	8
70	195	25
60	190	30
50	195	42
40	215	21
30	195	26
25	215	19
20	245	24
15	270	41
10	265	30
MAX	NIL	

HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 117
10 -64
15 -63
20 -67
T 188 -68

100	100	10
	120	13
35	120	19
80	110	12
70	130	6
60	305	8
50	290	19
40	250	15
30	235	16
25	250	18
20	245	24
15	275	33
10	275	20
MAX	NIL	